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Two-phase modelling of CO₂ droplet plumes

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1 Executive summary

This project, entitled

CO₂ injection in the ocean

was funded by the Norwegian Research Council, through the Klimatek program and G. C. Rieber Climate Institute. The project has been carried out at Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center, NERSC, and at Massachusetts Institute of Technology, MIT, Massachusetts, USA. Environmental profiles for the Keahole Pt. has been provided by Brian Crouse, MIT.

1.1 Background

The objective with this study has been to develop a three dimensional time dependent twophase model of droplets in a carrying fluid, and to use the model to study droplet plumes generated by injection of CO₂ in the ocean.

1.2 Motivation

Atmospheric CO₂ is one of several greenhouse gasses. The atmospheric concentration of CO₂ has increased from about 280 ppm (parts per million, or 0.028%) from the start of the industrial revolution to about 360 ppm today (Fig.2). This increase is mainly caused by burning of oil, coal, and gas. By this increase, the fossil fuel derived CO₂ in the atmosphere accounts for about two thirds of the increase in the global greenhouse gas forcing (Houghton *et al.*, 1996).

It is known that the World Oceans have the chemical capacity to absorb almost all of the known fossil fuel reserves (Broecker and Peng, 1982). However, the oceanic uptake of the excess atmospheric CO₂ is slow, thousands of years are required before equilibrium between the atmosphere, the ocean and the ocean sediments is achieved. Purposefully ocean storage of CO₂ can therefore be viewed as an acceleration of the natural ocean uptake of CO₂.

Carbon dioxide can be disposed off in the ocean in several ways; the option treated here is to collect CO₂ from exhaust gas or CO₂-containing natural gas, compress it so it becomes liquid (this occurs at about 57 bar at 20°C), transport it in a pipe to the desired injection site, and release it as droplets into the ocean through a diffuser device.

1.3 Droplet plumes, physics and modeling

Liquid CO₂ is less dense than seawater at ocean depth less than 3500 meters. If injected as droplets, a droplet plume will ascend in the water column and entrain water due to drag between the droplets and water. Gradually the CO₂ droplets dissolve transferring CO₂ into the plume water and, since CO₂-enriched water is more dens than the ambient water, the plume water will tend to descend in the water column. As ambient water dilutes the CO₂-enriched water by mixing, the density difference disappears, and the injected CO₂ follows the ocean dynamics as a dynamically passive tracer.

Several studies on the behaviour of such droplet plumes have been published in the last decade. Generally, the models differ only slightly; they are all steady state, they have to prescribe peeling events in order to maintain an upward buoyancy, and they cannot model the peeled off CO₂ enriched water.

The model presented here treats the liquid CO₂ as a second phase in an ordinary Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) code. The two phases interact through drag and mass transfer. Parameters from Keyhole Pt. Hawaii, and injection rates in the range planned for the CTI large scale experiment has been used in the numerical experiments presented, see Tab. 2

The numerical experiments indicate that the droplet size is a key parameter in order to predict the rising distance of the droplet plume. Increased radius increases the distance. Since lower rising distance influence less water masses with CO₂ the density difference increases with decreasing injection radius on the droplets. For very small droplets the CO₂ enriched water moves deeper than the injection site due to the increase in density. Larger background velocity exposes larger water masses to CO₂ and the density difference is less.

If fast dilution of the CO₂ enriched water is the objective large droplet sizes and high background current is preferable. On the other hand if the objective is to increase the density in order to generate a sinking plume of CO₂ enriched seawater, the CO₂ should be injected with small droplet radius and with low background current.

1.4 Outline of the report

The report starts with an introductory section on the carbon cycle, the increased atmospheric CO₂ concentration, the oceans role in the global carbon cycle, and environmental impacts from injecting CO₂ into water masses. Sec. 3 describes the two phase droplet model followed by results using environmental parameters from Keahole Pt., Hawaii in Sec. 4. Conclusions are drawn in Sec. 5. In Appendices physical properties of CO₂ in seawater are given and a test case of fresh water release into a stratified environment is shown. List of notation is given in a table on pp. 32

2 Introduction

2.1 The global carbon cycle and ocean disposal of CO₂

Air and sea surface measurements show that the the global surface temperature has increased by about 0.5°C over the last 140 years, and that the last decade has been the warmest in the period of the temperature record (Houghton *et al.*, 1996, and Fig. 1). Furthermore, statistical analysis indicates that the current decade is the first decade in which the greenhouse signal can be distinguished from the natural climate variability, and that it is likely that parts of the observed warming is related to the increased concentrations of atmospheric greenhouse gasses (Hasselmann *et al.*, 1995; Santer *et al.*, 1995; Houghton *et al.*, 1996).

Based on current knowledge of radiative processes in the atmosphere, it is believed that about two thirds of the man-generated greenhouse forcing is caused by increasing concentrations of atmospheric carbon dioxide (Fig. 2). An increasing human population, increased standard of living in the developing parts of the world, no alternative large-scale energy resources, and a known recoverable fossil fuel reserve of 3000–5000 Gt-C indicate that the man-made emissions of CO₂ will double or triple over the next century (Houghton *et al.*, 1996), and that the fossil fuel era may last for several centuries.

2.1.1 The ocean part of the global circulation

The world oceans play an important role in the global carbon cycle, and the oceanic waters and sediments have the capacity to absorb and neutralize all but a few percent of

Figure 1: Combined land air and sea surface temperatures relative to 1951–1980 averages (data from Jones *et al.* (1994) and Univ. of East Anglia, UK).

Figure 2: Evolution of the atmospheric concentration of CO₂ in parts per million (ppm) since the start of the industrial revolution. Data from Mauna Loa, Hawaii, are measured values; data from Siple Station, Antarctic, are deduced from air trapped in the Antarctic ice sheet. Data from Boden *et al.* (1993).

the amount of carbon locked up in the known, recoverable fossil fuel reserves (Broecker and Peng, 1982). However, the oceanic uptake of the excess atmospheric CO_2 is slow, thousands of years are required before equilibrium between the atmosphere, the ocean and the ocean sediments is achieved. The reason for the slow uptake of atmospheric CO_2 in the ocean is partly caused by the slow uptake of CO_2 through the mixed upper layer of the ocean, and partly in the low rate of mixing between the surface and sub-surface waters.

It was therefore proposed by Marchetti (1977) to collect and compress CO_2 from coal, oil and gas power plants, and to pipe and inject the CO_2 -fluid directly into the ocean. Marchetti identified the Strait of Gibraltar as a promising place; here the saline and dense outflowing Mediterranean water sinks to about 1000 m, and would therefore spread and dilute the CO_2 over practically all the Atlantic.

The paper by Marchetti was followed by Hoffert *et al.* (1979), who used a simple horizontally integrated box model and examined the atmospheric response of ocean disposal of CO_2 . Results from the Hoffert *et al.* paper are shown in Fig. 3. The model calculations are based

Figure 3: Modelled atmospheric concentration of CO_2 (in ppm) assuming that a fossil fuel reserve of 7×10^3 Gt C is burned. The curves indicate the atmospheric $p\text{CO}_2$ if all of the CO_2 is emitted to the atmosphere (upper curve), or if all of the CO_2 is injected at sea floor (lower curve). The figure is based on Fig. 4 in Hoffert *et al.* (1979).

on emission rates which are rather extreme (7000 Gt C released between year 1900 and year 2200, with a maximum emission rate in year 2060 corresponding to an increase in the atmospheric concentration of CO_2 of almost 90 ppm), but the results illustrate the effect of ocean disposal of CO_2 : By injecting CO_2 into the ocean, one can reduce the transient but not the final steady-state value of atmospheric CO_2 concentration. This result has been confirmed by Sundquist (1986) and Wilson (1992) in similar studies, and by Bacastow and Stegen (1991),

Maier-Reimer (1991), and Stegen *et al.* (1993) by using the global 3-dimensional ocean circulation and marine carbon cycle model of Maier-Reimer and Hasselmann (1987) and Bacastow and Maier-Reimer (1991).

2.1.2 Ocean disposal options

Several ocean disposal options have been proposed, and Fig. 4 gives a schematic illustration of the different options. Dry ice is always heavier than seawater and will sink. Hydrate is heavier

Figure 4: The different options that can be used for ocean disposal of CO₂. The arrows indicate the depth interval in which the injected CO₂ in gaseous, liquid, dissolved, or solid form will ascend or descend through the water column.

deeper than approx. 250 meters. CO₂ injected as droplets will be in gaseous form, forming bubbles, shallower than approx. 450 meters, and liquid if injected deeper. The droplets or bubbles will be less dense than seawater hence upward buoyant shallower than approx. 3000 meters, whereafter they become heavier. Once the CO₂ is dissolved in seawater the enriched seawater becomes heavier and tends to sink.

In this study it is assumed that the injection is shallower than 3000 meters and since the density of liquid CO₂ is less than that of ambient water for this depth interval, a chimney-like plume of CO₂-droplets and entrained seawater will rise through the water column over the injection site (Thorkildsen *et al.*, 1994b).

Since CO₂-enriched seawater has a density above that of ambient water (Drange and Haugan, 1992a; Haugan and Drange, 1992; Drange *et al.*, 1993; and Fig. (4)), the plume water will descend in the water column, entrain ambient water, and finally spread out in the horizontal where the density of the CO₂-enriched water reaches that of the ambient water, or on the ocean floor if the density of the plume water is sufficiently high.

2.2 Environmental impact of Ocean Disposal on marine life

As CO₂ dissolves in water, carbonic acid is formed, which then dissociates and forms bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻) and carbonate (CO₃²⁻) ions. Through this process, the pH of the water is reduced. It is therefore of importance to assess possible effects on marine organisms as CO₂ is injected into seawater.

Based on numerical simulations, it is found that the close vicinity of the injection site will be characterized by a pH-value of about 5.5 (natural seawater has a pH of 8±0.2). However, as ambient seawater is mixed into the CO₂-enriched water, the pH-value increases. As CO₂ is dissolved in seawater, the pH-value of the CO₂-enriched water decreases (Fig. 5). The marine biota is sensitive to changes in the pH-value of the water since natural seawater has a relative constant pH-value of about 8 (natural variations are typically bracketed by 0.1–0.2 pH-units). It is therefore important to quantify the consequences ocean disposal of CO₂ may have on the marine biota. The environmental impacts of lowered pH-value depend on two parameters: The actual reduction of the pH-value compared to ambient conditions, and the pH-exposure (Auerbach *et al.*, 1996). An indication of the mortality of different marine zooplankton and benthos as function of time exposed to different pH-values is shown in Fig. 6. Based on the % mortality shown in Fig. 6, Auerbach *et al.* (1996) indicate the 0, 50, and 90% mortality curves as seen in Fig. 7. Figures 6 and 7 clearly indicate that the environmental stress marine organisms experience depend on exposed time and the actual pH value.

It is important to realize that different groups will respond to lowered pH-value in different ways. Pörtner and Reipschläger (1996) discuss two marine species, one tolerant (the large worm *Sipunculus nudus*) and one intolerant (the open ocean squid *Illex illecebrosus*) organism. Whereas the first one may tolerate pH levels as low as 6.5, the latter one shows sub-lethal (lethal) effects for a 0.15 (0.25) reduction in the pH-value. In general, a pH-value of 7.0 is likely to have significant sub-lethal effects even on the most tolerant of marine organisms (Ormerod and Angel (1996), p. 18). Further, based on our knowledge of inshore coastal species indicates that a pH of 7.5 would be the lower limit for many species (Ormerod and Angel (1996), p. 35).

The International Energy Agency (IEA) workshop *Ocean Storage of Carbon Dioxide - Environmental Impact* concludes that (Ormerod and Angel (1996), p. 39–40)

To prevent acute loss of marine organisms, reduction in water pH below 7.0 should only be tolerated temporarily or in small areas and, if feasible, a water pH below 7.5 should be avoided.

This conclusion is consistent with the findings of Magnesen (1993), and Stenevik and Giske (1997); that a reduction of pH to about 7.5 is tolerable to some marine organisms at least in the short term.

Based on the above considerations we may define the environmental impact of lowered pH value according to the classes:

Figure 5: Computed pH -value as CO_2 is dissolved in seawater at a pressure of 35 bar and a temperature of $8^\circ C$. ΔC_T (mol-C m⁻³) denotes the amount of carbon added to in seawater. Natural seawater has a pH -value of about 8, and it contains about 2 mol-C m⁻³, so $\Delta C_T = 2$ mol-C m⁻³ represents a doubling of the amount of dissolved inorganic carbon in seawater. The pH -value of small values of ΔC_T has been enhanced by using different linear scalings of the x -axis.

$\Delta pH \leq 0.1$: Small or no effect on marine biota (note, however, that some organisms experience sub-lethal effects at a continuous lowering of the pH -value of 0.15, Pörtner and Reipschläger, 1996)

$0.1 \leq \Delta pH \leq 0.5$: Increasing effect on marine biota; small effect for short-time exposures

$0.5 \leq \Delta pH \leq 1$: Sub-lethal effects on most organisms, medium effect for short-time exposures

$1 \leq \Delta pH$: Lethal effects on most organisms, sub-lethal effect for short-time exposures

Obviously, the effect of acidified water on marine organisms will depend on the type of organisms considered. For instance, benthic organisms will not be able to escape from acidified water, and will therefore die if the organisms are continuously exposed to low pH water. Most of the plankton organisms are not able to swim, so they are transported by the water masses. In the worst case, plankton organisms may enter the CO_2 -enriched water at the injection site, and will remain in the center of the CO_2 -plume. This means, for a 20 km long plume and for a background current of 5 cm s^{-1} , that the organisms will stay in the plume for about 4.5 days, or 110 hours. During this time, the organisms will first experience rather acid water

Figure 6: Mortality in % for some marine zooplankton and benthos groups as function of pH and exposed time (from Auerbach *et al.*, 1996).

Figure 7: 0, 50, and 90% mortality curves based on the discrete mortality points in Fig. 6. The asymptotic values are drawn, somewhat arbitrarily, at a pH of 7.5, 6.8 and 6.3 for 0, 50, and 100% mortality, respectively (from Auerbach *et al.*, 1996).

(at the injection point), and gradually less acid water as the injected carbon is mixed with ambient water. Marine organisms that are able to swim, including fish, will tend to move away from the CO₂-enriched water. In addition, adult fish seems to be relatively tolerant to a slight reduction in the pH value of the water due to the low metabolic rate of fish. This is, however, not the case for fish eggs and larvae. Therefore, regions where fish eggs and larvae occur should be avoided.

2.3 Droplet plume modeling

The rising plume resulting from releasing CO₂ droplet below 400 meters depth has so far been modeled by primitive bulk models (Liro *et al.*, 1992; Drange and Haugan, 1992b; Thorkildsen and Haugan, 1993, 1994a). The buoyancy of the droplets will be counteracted by increasing density of the entrained plume water. But even when the total buoyancy over the cross section of the plume reaches zero the droplets will continue to rise. To account for this, these models perform a peeling event in which the dense plume water is ejected from the plume. The peeled off water is heavier than the surrounding water and hence will sink in the water column, however this motion is not accounted for in the bulk models. In a first attempt to model the ejected water Thorkildsen and Alendal (1997) placed a source of buoyancy and dissolved CO₂ in a three dimensional Navier Stokes solver. This study showed that the CO₂ enriched plume water can sink below the release depth. In Drange *et al.* (1998) this approach where used to model a release of CO₂ on Haltenbanken off the coast of Norway. Background current transport the dissolved CO₂ downstream, and taking the distribution as input to an ordinary diffusion model makes it possible to include a CO₂ injection source into a large scale regional ocean model.

However, still a bulk model where used for the droplet plume, the droplets stayed in a vertical column, unaffected by the background current and the downward motion of dense water on the rim of the plume. Evolution of the combined rising droplets and sinking seawater is the scope of this study. The droplets will be treated as a second phase interacting with the seawater. The two phases interact through mass transfer from the liquid CO₂ droplets to the seawater, and through drag between droplets and water.

3 The two-phase model

This section gives a description of the two-phase droplet model. Hereafter the seawater will be denoted by the carrier or continuous phase, while the CO₂ droplets will be called the dispersed phase. The model originates from Crowe *et al.* (1998) which supply a set of equations to be solved for a two-phase flow where both phases are treated as continuum. Each phase are described by continuity and momentum equations. The carrier phase has in addition tracer equations for temperature, salinity, and dissolved CO₂. A number density equation is used to close the system of differential equations. The model equations are displayed in Tab. 1, and the nomenclature is given on p. 32.

Description of the two phases will be done separately; Sec. 3.1 treats the equations for the carrier phase, followed by dispersed phase equations in Sec. 3.2, and finally parameters are treated in Sec. 3.3. This section concludes with a discussion on limitations, solution methods and initialization of the model (Sec. 3.4). But first a few definitions:

Number density

$$n = \lim_{\partial V \rightarrow \partial V_0} \frac{\partial N}{\partial V} \quad [m^{-3}] \quad (1)$$

where ∂N [1] is the number of elements in the volume ∂V [m^3] while ∂V_0 [m^3] is the limiting volume that assures stationary average.

Volume fractions

$$\alpha_d = \lim_{\partial V \rightarrow \partial V_0} \frac{\partial V_d}{\partial V} \quad [1] \quad (2)$$

where ∂V_d [m^3] is the volume of the dispersed phase in the control volume, similar for the continuous phase, also called the void fraction:

$$\alpha_c = \lim_{\partial V \rightarrow \partial V_0} \frac{\partial V_c}{\partial V} \quad [1] \quad (3)$$

The relationship

$$\alpha_d + \alpha_c = 1 \quad (4)$$

assures consistency.

In the following all droplets are assumed to be of the same size with volume V_d [m^3] in each control volume, hence $\partial V_d = \partial N V_d$ and

$$\alpha_d = \lim_{\partial V \rightarrow \partial V_0} \frac{\partial N V_d}{\partial V} = n V_d \quad (5)$$

Bulk density or apparent density

$$\bar{\rho}_d = \lim_{\partial V \rightarrow \partial V_0} \frac{\partial M_d}{\partial V} \quad [kg \ m^{-3}] \quad (6)$$

where ∂M_d [kg] is the mass of the dispersed phase in the control volume. Correspondingly there is a definition for bulk density of the continuous phase, $\bar{\rho}_c$.

If all particles have the same mass, m [kg],

$$\bar{\rho}_d = n m_d = \alpha_d \rho_d \quad [kg \ m^{-3}] \quad (7)$$

3.1 The carrier phase

According to Crowe *et al.* (1998) the following equations should be solved for the carrier phase; a continuity equation:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \alpha_c \rho_c + \nabla \cdot \alpha_c \rho_c \mathbf{u} = -s_{mass} \quad (8)$$

and momentum equations:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \alpha_c \rho_c \mathbf{u} + \nabla \cdot \alpha_c \rho_c \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u} = -\alpha_c \nabla p + \alpha_c \rho_c \mathbf{g} + \alpha_c \nabla \cdot \tilde{\tau} - \beta_V (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}) - \mathbf{v} s_{mass} \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{u}$ [$m \ s^{-1}$] is the velocity vector for the carrier phase, ρ_c [$kg \ m^{-3}$] the carrier phase density, $\mathbf{g}$ [$m \ s^{-2}$] the gravitational vector, and $\tilde{\tau}$ [Pa] is the stress tensor. Drag from the

dispersed phase enters through drag proportional to the velocity difference between the two phases with a drag coefficient $\beta_V [kg\ m^{-3}\ s^{-1}]$, and $\mathbf{v} [m\ s^{-1}]$ is droplet or dispersed velocity. The last term represents momentum added to the carrier phase from diffused mass from the dispersed phase. The mass transfer, denoted $s_{mass} [kg\ s^{-1}]$, is treated in Sec. 3.3.5.

In order to use an already existing Navier Stokes solver these equations have to be rewritten.

3.1.1 Continuity equation

Differentiating through the continuity equation gives

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \rho_c \alpha_c + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \rho_c \alpha_c + \rho_c \alpha_c \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = -s_{mass} \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \rho_c \alpha_c + \rho_c \alpha_c \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = -s_{mass} \quad (11)$$

The change in mass for the continuous phase is all due to the dissolution of the dispersed phase, i.e.,

$$\frac{d}{dt} \rho_c \alpha_c = -s_{mass} \quad (12)$$

leaving the ordinary non-compressible continuity equation

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (13)$$

3.1.2 Momentum equation

In the same manner the momentum equation is differentiated as

$$\mathbf{u} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \bar{\rho}_c + \nabla \cdot \bar{\rho}_c \mathbf{u} \right) + \bar{\rho}_c \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} \right) = -\alpha_c \nabla p + \rho_c \mathbf{g} + \nabla \cdot \tilde{\tau} - \beta_V (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}) - \mathbf{v} s_{mass} \quad (14)$$

Recognizing the continuity equation in the first term on the l.h.s and using the Boussinesq approximation, i.e. dividing through with a characteristic density ρ_0 and neglecting density variations in all terms apart from in the gravity term, yields

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} = -\nabla p + \frac{\rho_c}{\rho_0} \mathbf{g} + \nabla \cdot \frac{\tilde{\tau}}{\rho_0} - \frac{\beta_V}{\rho_0 \alpha_c} (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}) + s_{mass} (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}) \quad (15)$$

The last term has been neglected.

3.1.3 Tracer equations

Neglecting heat from the dissolution process the tracer equations for salinity $S [psu]$ and temperature $T [^\circ C]$ can be put in the form

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} T + \nabla \cdot T \mathbf{u} = \nabla \cdot \kappa_T^e \nabla T \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} S + \nabla \cdot S \mathbf{u} = \nabla \cdot \kappa_S^e \nabla S \quad (17)$$

where κ_T^e [$m^2 s^{-1}$] and κ_S^e [$m^2 s^{-1}$] are temperature and salinity turbulent diffusivity, see Sec. 3.3.4. For the CO_2 tracer a source term has to enter the equation due to dissolution of CO_2 from the droplets, so

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} C + \nabla \cdot C \mathbf{u} = \nabla \cdot \kappa_C^e \nabla C - s_{mass}/M_{CO_2} \quad (18)$$

where M_{CO_2} [$kg mole^{-1}$] is the molar mass of CO_2 , see Sec. 3.3.1.

3.2 The dispersed phase

3.2.1 Continuity equation

The continuity equation for the dispersed phase is similar to the carrier phase with opposite sign on the mass transfer and with an additional term for the injection of mass through droplets (I_{mass} [$kg m^{-3} s^{-1}$])

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \alpha_d \rho_d + \nabla \cdot \alpha_d \rho_d \mathbf{u} = s_{mass} + I_{mass} \quad (19)$$

3.2.2 Momentum equation

A momentum equation for the dispersed phase can also be given but so far the dispersed droplets are assumed to move with the carrier phase with an additional vertical terminal velocity, see Sec. 3.3.6, so

$$\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{u} + U_T \mathbf{k}; \quad (20)$$

where $\mathbf{k}$ is a unit vector in the vertical direction.

3.2.3 Number density equation

In order to close the number equations a number density equation has been used. The rate of change of number density depends on the flux of droplets in and out of the volume and the number injected I_n [$kg m^{-3} s^{-1}$] (Ferziger and Perić, 1997)

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_{V_0} n d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma_0} n \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{m} dS = \int_{V_0} I_n d\Omega. \quad (21)$$

Here V_0 [m^3] and Γ_0 [m^2] are volume and surface area of the control volume, respectively, and the surface normal vector is denoted $\mathbf{m}$. Using Gauss law on the surface integral and collecting all the terms under the same integral yields

$$\int_{V_0} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} n + \nabla \cdot n \mathbf{v} - I_n \right) d\Omega = 0. \quad (22)$$

As long as a stationary average can be reached, the control volume can be chosen arbitrary giving an equation for the number density

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} n + \nabla \cdot n \mathbf{v} = I_n \quad (23)$$

Model equations		
Carrier phase		
$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0$	Continuity equation	Ref. Sec. 3.1.1
$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{u} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}\mathbf{u} = -\nabla p + \frac{\rho_c}{\rho_0} \mathbf{g} + \nabla \cdot \tilde{\boldsymbol{\tau}} - \beta_V U_T$	Momentum equation	Ref. Sec. 3.1.2
$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} T + \nabla \cdot T\mathbf{u} = \nabla \cdot \kappa_T^e \nabla T$	Tracer equation temperature	Ref. Sec. 3.1.3
$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} S + \nabla \cdot S\mathbf{u} = \nabla \cdot \kappa_S^e \nabla S$	Tracer equation salinity	Ref. Sec. 3.1.3
$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} C + \nabla \cdot C\mathbf{u} = \nabla \cdot \kappa_C^e \nabla C - \frac{s_{mass}}{M_{CO_2}}$	Tracer equation dissolved CO ₂	Ref. Sec. 3.1.3
Dispersed phase		
$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \alpha_d \rho_d + \nabla \cdot \alpha_d \rho_d \mathbf{v} = s_{mass} + I_{mass}$	continuity equation	Ref. Sec. 3.2.1
$\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{u} + U_T \mathbf{k}$	"Momentum equation"	Ref. Sec. 3.2.2
$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} n + \nabla \cdot n\mathbf{v} = I_n$	Number density equation	Ref. Sec. 3.2.3

Table 1: Model equations, notation is listed on pp. 32

3.3 Parameters

3.3.1 Equation of state

The ordinary UNESCO equation of state (UNESCO, 1981) has to be extended to take account for the increased CO₂ concentration (Drange and Haugan, 1992a)

$$\rho_c = \rho_{UNESCO}(S, T, p) + (M_{CO_2} - \rho_{UNESCO}(S, T, p)v_{CO_2})C \quad (24)$$

where $M_{CO_2} = 44.01 \times 10^{-3} [kg \text{ mole}^{-1}]$ and $v_{CO_2} = 34 \times 10^{-6} [m^3 \text{ mole}^{-1}]$ are, respectively, the molar mass and volume of CO₂. In the pressure range considered here these parameters vary little so they have been treated as constants.

A rather lengthy equation of state is used for the density of the liquid CO₂ and is given in App. A.1.

3.3.2 The stress tensor

For the stress tensor a Smagorinsky stress has been used with proportionality to the shear (McComb, 1990):

$$\tau_{ij} = -\rho_0 \nu_e \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \bar{u}_j}{\partial x_i} \right), \quad (25)$$

with a local eddy viscosity

$$\nu_e = c^2 \Delta^2 \tilde{S}^{1/2}, \quad (26)$$

c being a constant, Δ filter width taken to be the gridspacing, and

$$\tilde{S} = \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \bar{u}_k}{\partial x_i} \right), \quad (27)$$

is the shear. This model has been used in this study with $c = 0.079$

3.3.3 Friction term

The drag coefficient has been taken from the development of the slip velocity, treated in Sec. 3.3.6, which assume that the droplets move with a terminal velocity, denoted U_T [$m s^{-1}$], under the assumption of drag and buoyancy balance. The buoyancy on a droplet is, assuming the gravity works in the vertical direction only,

$$F_G = V_d g (\rho_c - \rho_d) \quad (28)$$

which has to balance the drag force on one particle

$$F_D = \beta_d (u - v) = \beta_d u_T. \quad (29)$$

For each particle then the drag coefficient is

$$\beta_d = \frac{V_d g (\rho_c - \rho_d)}{u_T}. \quad (30)$$

Summing over all the droplets in a control volume and dividing with the volume gives the drag coefficient in Eq. (14)

$$\beta_V = \frac{n V_d g (\rho_c - \rho_d)}{u_T} = \frac{\alpha_d g (\rho_c - \rho_d)}{u_T} \quad (31)$$

3.3.4 Turbulent diffusivity

Yakhot and Orszag (1986) provides a turbulent or eddy diffusivity based on ReNormalization Group (RNG) theory

$$\left| \frac{\phi - 1.3929}{\phi_0 - 1.3929} \right|^{0.6321} \left| \frac{\phi + 2.3929}{\phi_0 + 2.3929} \right|^{0.3679} = \frac{\nu_0}{\nu_e} \quad (32)$$

where

$$\phi = \frac{\kappa_S^e}{\nu_e}, \quad \phi_0 = \frac{\kappa_S^0}{\nu_0} \quad (33)$$

are respectively the turbulent and molecular inverse Prandtl numbers, in this case for salinity but similar for the other two scalars. Notice if the turbulent viscosity equals the molecular viscosity, $\nu_e = \nu_0$, the turbulent diffusivity equals the molecular diffusivity, $\kappa_S^e = \kappa_S^0$. In the other extreme where the turbulent viscosity is much larger than the molecular viscosity the fraction on the r.h.s of Eq. (32) approach zero giving a turbulent diffusivity of $\kappa_S^e = 1.3929$. The equation involves solving a nonlinear equation at each node for each timestep so the solutions for Eq. (32) have therefore been evaluated once for the range

$$0 < \frac{\nu_0}{\nu_e} \leq 1 \Rightarrow \kappa_S^0 \leq \kappa_S^e \leq 1.3929$$

and stored in an array.

3.3.5 Masstransfer

According to Drange and Haugan (1992a) the mass transfer from one droplet with radius r [m] is

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{4}{3} \rho_d r^3 \right) = -4\pi r^2 K M_{\text{CO}_2} (C_s - C_0) \quad (34)$$

where $C_s = 1363.33$ [mole m^{-3}], has been assumed to be a constant. The mass transfer coefficient, K [$m s^{-1}$] has been taken from Clift *et al.* (1978):

$$K = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \left(1 - \frac{2.89}{\sqrt{Re_k}} \right) \sqrt{\frac{\kappa_C^0 U_T}{2r}} [kg s^{-1}] \quad (35)$$

where

$$Re_k = \frac{2\rho_d r U_b}{\nu_0}, \quad (36)$$

is a dimensionless Reynolds number. This is the masstransfer from a single droplet, whereas the mass transfer pr. unit volume is obtained by multiplying with the number density

$$s_{mass} = n4\pi r^2 K M_{\text{CO}_2} (C_s - C) [kg m^{-3} s^{-1}] \quad (37)$$

3.3.6 Terminal or slip velocity of the droplets

A particle in stagnant fluid will be influenced by buoyancy and drag on the droplet interface. When these forces balance the droplets move with a constant settling or slip velocity. In the present study the terminal velocity presented by Clift *et al.* (1978):

$$U_T = 0.711 \sqrt{2rg \frac{\rho_c - \rho_d}{\rho_c}} \quad (38)$$

has been used. This equation is valid for liquid gas droplets with radius larger than 0.5 mm. For smaller droplets the terminal velocity is set to zero. In all the numerical experiments presented later, the droplets stay below the transition to gaseous phase depth at approx. 450 meters.

3.3.7 Droplet radius

Since volume of droplets equals

$$V_d = \frac{4}{3}\pi r^3 \quad (39)$$

the radius of the droplets follows from Eq. (5)

$$r = \left(\frac{\alpha_d}{\frac{4}{3}\pi n} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (40)$$

3.4 Limitations, solution method and initialization

Some assumptions has been made while developing the model. First, the droplets are not interacting with each other, i.e. there is no merging to create larger droplets. Secondly, in each control volume, in practice the grid nodes, all droplets have been assumed to be of the same size. This can be argued to be an average droplet size. However, since the largest droplets moves with a higher slip velocity these droplets will leave the node, hence enter the neighboring node, faster than the smaller ones. This is not accounted for in the present model.

Hydrate formation on the droplets will reduce the mass transfer. This can be accounted for by reducing the mass transfer coefficient but this has not been done in the calculations presented here.

There is no equation for the pressure term in Eq. (14). The most frequently used assumption in large scale ocean models is the hydrostatic approximation which reduces the vertical momentum equation to a hydrostatic balance equation. This assumption is valid for events on large horizontal scale but for smaller scales and for events with high vertical motion this assumption is no longer valid (see for instance Marshall *et al.*, 1997). The momentum and continuity equations lack an explicit equation for the pressure which has to be solved implicit. Several methods exist but most of them use the continuity equation, Eq. (13), to find a pressure field that enforce solenoidal (divergence free) velocity field. A fractional timestep method (Ferziger and Perić, 1997) has been used; first the momentum equations are solved using the old pressure field, the resulting velocity field is generally not solenoidal and is updated by using a new pressure field that enforce no divergence in the new velocity field. This involves solving of an elliptic problem for the pressure field, which has been done using a multigrid method.

4 Results

The numerical experiments use temperature and salinity profiles from Keahole Pt. located on Hawaii which is selected as the site of the CTI large scale ocean CO₂ disposal field experiment. The site has pipelines already installed for other purposes and they will be used for the experiment. The environmental profile is given in Fig. (8) (Adams and Herzog, 1997; Adams and Herzog, 1998). The background velocity varies both due to tidal influence but also from mesoscale eddies in the vicinity of the island. The velocity can reach 10 *cms*⁻¹. The numerical experiments vary injected droplet radius, background current and injection rate, based on a Base Case with droplet radius 7 *mm*, background current 5 *cm s*⁻¹ and 1 *kg s*⁻¹ injection rate. Key parameters for the different numerical experiments are given in Tab. 2.

Figure 8: Density profile off Keahole Pt., Hawaii.

Model experiments

Key	Background velocity $m s^{-1}$	droplet radius m	injection rate $kgCO_2 s^{-1}$
B(ase)	0.05	0.007	1.0
R01	0.05	0.001	1.0
R12	0.05	0.012	1.0
U00	0.00	0.007	1.0
U10	0.10	0.007	1.0
Ra01	0.05	0.007	0.1

Table 2: Key parameters for the different experiments.

4.1 Extended discussion on the Base Case

As the droplets are released they ascend in the water column and drift downstream with the background current field. Gradually they dissolve and the water in the vicinity of the droplet experience increasing CO_2 concentration, hence lowered pH, and increased density. The increase in density leads to a downward motion of the water that will retard the rising of the droplets. If the velocity of the sinking water exceed the terminal velocity of the droplets they will also sink. Fig. (9) shows time evolution of the number density of droplets. Each panel is taken 5 minutes apart and notice the logarithmic contour spacing. The droplets rise approx. 60 meters above the injection point. Here the radius reaches the threshold where the terminal velocity is set to zero ($r = 0.5 \times 10^{-3} (m)$) whereafter they follow the mainstream. We can also see that downstream the number density moves downward again due to descending CO_2 enriched water. Fig. (10) shows, also with logarithmic contour spacing, the total mass of free CO_2 in the droplets for the grid cells. This figure shows that the major part of the CO_2

has been transferred to the seawater some 50 meters downstream. The remaining droplets shown in Fig. (9) are small droplets with little CO_2 . The corresponding pH-field is shown in Fig. (11), notice how the reduced pH water sinks below the droplets. The CO_2 enriched water populates a layer of approx. 80 meter for the base case starting ~ 20 meters below the injection depth. The lowest pH value, which is also the most dense, will naturally be found close to the injection site.

4.2 Comparison between the experiments

The different experiments shown in Tab. 2 differs in radius of the injected droplets and background velocity, with only one parameter altered at the time.

4.2.1 Differing droplet radius

As the droplet radius increase the terminal velocity, or slip velocity, increases, hence droplets with large radius ascend faster in the water column than smaller droplets. As the CO_2 enriched water starts to sink small droplets follow the descending water at lower vertical water velocity than larger droplets. Fig. (12) shows snapshots of the total mass of free CO_2 in each gridcell and pH-field at 35 minutes for the experiments with different droplet radius. When the injected droplet radius is small, as in Exp. R01 (Middle panel Fig. (12)), the droplets descend in the water column and spread below the injection site. For large radius on the injected droplets, Exp. R12 (Lower panel Fig. (12)), the droplet plume rise further than for the Base experiment. Notice also how the droplet plume in this experiment goes out of the modeling domain at the upper boundary. It also seems like smaller droplets decreases the vertical thickness of the low pH layer.

4.2.2 Varying background velocity

When the background velocity is changed the droplet plume bends more for high compared to low velocities. Fig. (13) shows similar figures as in the previous section. Notice the different horizontal scale on the U00 experiment, upper panel in Fig. (13). With no background velocity the droplet plume ascend vertically while the dense plume water sinks to the bottom where it spreads. The droplet plume and the descending water will not experience as much dilution since there is no background velocity to transport droplets and CO_2 away from the injection site, i.e., less water masses are in touch with the CO_2 droplets. With high background velocity, Exp. U10 (middle panel in Fig. (13)), the droplet plume spreads further down stream. However the droplets rise to approx. the same distance and the layer with lowered pH stays nearly the same.

4.2.3 Low injection rate

The last experiment are shown in the lower panel of Fig. (13). In this experiment the injection rate of CO_2 are 10 % of the Base experiment so the droplet plume are smaller but still rise 45 meter in the vertical. Notice how the diluted water does not go below the injection depth. The injection rate are too low to give a large density difference between the CO_2 enriched water and the ambient water, hence little or no sinking. Similar picture can be achieved if CO_2 is injected at the same rate as the Base Case but through 10 ports instead of one.

Figure 9: Time evolution of the number density field.

Figure 10: Time evolution of the mass of free CO₂ in droplets.

Figure 11: Time evolution of the pH-field.

Figure 12: Density of free CO₂ in the droplets (left) and pH field (right) after 35 minutes

4.3 Volume of water with reduced pH

According to the discussion on p. 6 volume of water affected with reduced pH should be low in order to minimize influence on marine life. Fig. (14) show the volume of seawater that experience reduction in pH-value by 0.1, 0.5 and 1 pH-units, taking a sampling box 100 meters downstream from the injection site. Comparing the experiments with different droplet radius; Shows that for a modest pH reduction of 0.1 and 0.5 pH unit, the curves follow each other until a steady state is reached after ~ 35 minutes. The smaller volume for the R12 case is most likely caused by droplets leaving the modeling domain, Fig 12. However the reduction of the large pH reduction volume for the R12 case can be caused by the increased terminal velocity of the larger droplets. Note that larger droplets dissolve over a larger vertical distance hence dilute a larger water mass.

(c) Exp. Ra01 Left panel free CO₂ in the droplets, right pH-fieldFigure 13: Density of free CO₂ in the droplets and pH field after 35 minutes for different background velocity and 10 % injection rate

Figure 14: Volume ($\times 10^3 m^3$) with reduced pH. Upper panels show pH-reduction of 0.1 and 0.5 units while the lower panels shows volume with 1 pH-unit reduction. Labels from Tab. 2

For varying background velocity the highest velocity reaches a steady state after ~ 20 minutes. Until that time the affected volume stays above the Base Case curve since the CO_2 is transported faster downstream. However, the resulting steady state is smaller than the Base Case. The experiment with no velocity do not reach a steady state within the time frame of the experiment. There is background current to transport the CO_2 out of the sampling, and as can be seen in Fig. (15) the CO_2 reaches the bottom at 750 meters and spread over the sea floor. In this experiment the difference between the three curves are not as high as for the other cases, the CO_2 stays in the vicinity of the plume area and less dilution is taking place.

The volume of reduced pH when the injection rate is reduced by a factor 10 is much lower, there are an order of magnitude less CO_2 in the water masses.

To see how the CO_2 is distributed in the vertical, Fig. (15) shows the fraction of the total CO_2 in the sampling box as function of depth. The escape of some of the CO_2 in the R12 case can be seen. Also notice how the CO_2 is distributed deeper for the low radius case, R01. Low injection rate narrows the CO_2 layer. Higher background currents also narrow the CO_2

Figure 15: Distribution of CO₂ in the water column, percent of total CO₂ in the sampling box.

layer essentially by moving the lower boundary to shallower depths. The no velocity case, U00, reaches and spreads at the floor at 750 meters.

5 Conclusions

Six numerical experiments have been performed with varying droplet radius, background velocity and injection rate. The different radius experiments show that increasing initial droplet radius increases the vertical rise of the droplets. For low droplet radius the velocity of the descending CO₂ enriched seawater exceeds the terminal velocity of the droplets, hence the droplets will be transported downward in the water column. The layer of reduced pH levels out on deeper depth for decreasing droplet radius. Increasing background velocity bends the droplet plume and transports the droplets further downstream before they vanish. However it has little effect of the total vertical thickness of the low pH layer except that the lowest pH-value extend further downstream.

If fast dillution of the CO₂ enriched water is the aim, large droplet sizes and high background current are preferable. On the other hand, if the objective is to increase the density in order to generate a sinking plume of CO₂ enriched seawater, the CO₂ should be injected with small droplet radius and with low background currents.

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A Physical properties of CO₂ enriched sea water and CO₂ droplets.

A.1 Equation of state for CO₂

We are using an equation of state for CO₂ from Ely *et al.* (1989) which is based on comprehensive isochoric (p, ρ_{CO_2}, T) measurements for pure CO₂. This equation (41) with coefficients $A_i, i = 1, \dots, 15$ from Tab. 3 and $b_i, i = 1, \dots, 32$ from Tab. 4, is a 32-term equation of the form suggested by Jacobsen and Stewart, a modified Benedict-Webb-Rubin equation of state.

$$P = \sum_{i=1}^9 A_i \rho_{\text{CO}_2}^i + \exp\left(-\frac{\gamma \rho_{\text{CO}_2}^2}{\rho_{\text{cr}}^2}\right) \sum_{i=10}^{15} A_i \rho_{\text{CO}_2}^{(2i-17)} \quad (41)$$

where ρ_{CO_2} is density, and ρ_{cr} is critical density of CO₂. The range of state points for pure CO₂ included in evaluating this equation, are temperatures from 250 to 330 K and pressure up to 33 MPa. This is greater than the temperature and pressure range in our sea area.

The equation of state (41) for pressure p , does not increase monotonically with increasing density ρ_{CO_2} . It is possible to show a good agreement between (41) and other data sets for the density interval $\rho \in [1, 160] \cup [900, 1100] \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$, see e.g. (Drange and Haugan, 1992c). This leads us to use (41) in these intervals and to use a polynomial interpolation at the phase change.

The condensation pressure P_{cond} (bar) depends on the temperature according to Drange and Haugan (1992c):

$$P_{\text{cond}} = 34.8649 + 0.90485T_c + 0.0108504T_c^2. \quad (42)$$

where T_c is temperature in degree Celsius.

We introduce a third degree polynomial interpolation over a pressure interval $P \in [P_{\text{cond}} - I, P_{\text{cond}} + I]$,

$$\rho_{\text{CO}_2} = (1 - f)\rho_{\text{liquid}} + f\rho_{\text{gas}} \quad (43)$$

where

$$f = 3 \left(\frac{P_{\text{cond}} - P + I}{2I} \right)^2 - 2 \left(\frac{P_{\text{cond}} - P + I}{2I} \right)^3 \quad (44)$$

and $\rho_{\text{gas}}, \rho_{\text{liquid}}$ are calculated from (41) in the interval $\rho_{\text{gas}} \in [1 : 160]$ and $\rho_{\text{liquid}} \in [900 : 1100]$ respectively. The equation of state using (41), solved with respect to ρ_{CO_2} with an Illinois algorithm implemented by Guttorm Alendal at NERSC, and the interpolated version (43) are plotted with $I=1$ (bar) and $T_c = 10$ °C in Fig. ??.

$A_1 = RT$	$A_6 = \frac{b_{14}}{T} + \frac{b_{15}}{T^2}$	$A_{11} = \frac{b_{22}}{T^2} + \frac{b_{23}}{T^4}$
$A_2 = b_1 T + b_2 T^{\frac{1}{2}} + b_3 + \frac{b_4}{T} + \frac{b_5}{T^{\frac{3}{2}}}$	$A_7 = \frac{b_{16}}{T}$	$A_{12} = \frac{b_{24}}{T^2} + \frac{b_{25}}{T^3}$
$A_3 = b_6 T + b_7 + \frac{b_8}{T} + \frac{b_9}{T^2}$	$A_8 = \frac{b_{17}}{T} + \frac{b_{18}}{T^2}$	$A_{13} = \frac{b_{26}}{T^2} + \frac{b_{27}}{T^4}$
$A_4 = b_{10} T + b_{11} + \frac{b_{12}}{T}$	$A_9 = \frac{b_{19}}{T^{\frac{3}{2}}}$	$A_{14} = \frac{b_{28}}{T^2} + \frac{b_{29}}{T^3}$
$A_5 = b_{13}$	$A_{10} = \frac{b_{20}}{T^{\frac{3}{2}}} + \frac{b_{21}}{T^3}$	$A_{15} = \frac{b_{30}}{T^2} + \frac{b_{31}}{T^3} + \frac{b_{32}}{T^4}$

Table 3: Temperature dependency of the coefficients in the Modified Benedict-Webb-Rubin-32 equation of state (41) for pure CO₂. The Coefficients b_i are given in Tab. 4.

$b_1 = -0.164147038534 \times 10^{-2}$	$b_{12} = 0.513786291437 \times 10^{-1}$	$b_{23} = 0.201313458725 \times 10^7$
$b_2 = 0.145929294249$	$b_{13} = 0.399290811531 \times 10^{-4}$	$b_{24} = 0.183678443072 \times 10^1$
$b_3 = -0.322567667165 \times 10^1$	$b_{14} = -0.672823309226 \times 10^{-2}$	$b_{25} = -0.683851238480 \times 10^1$
$b_4 = 0.420707873671 \times 10^3$	$b_{15} = 0.902241252782 \times 10^1$	$b_{26} = 0.389996843596 \times 10^{-2}$
$b_5 = -0.459593803667 \times 10^5$	$b_{16} = 0.260383108327 \times 10^{-3}$	$b_{27} = -0.678673537499$
$b_6 = 0.440698210123 \times 10^{-4}$	$b_{17} = -0.278016427941 \times 10^{-5}$	$b_{28} = 0.454450104416 \times 10^{-5}$
$b_7 = -0.355905419463 \times 10^{-1}$	$b_{18} = -0.148694555399 \times 10^{-1}$	$b_{29} = 0.329755873375 \times 10^{-4}$
$b_8 = 0.175125702459 \times 10^1$	$b_{19} = 0.254880656162 \times 10^{-3}$	$b_{30} = 0.583216588973 \times 10^{-8}$
$b_9 = -0.681045405840 \times 10^5$	$b_{20} = 0.737790214963 \times 10^5$	$b_{31} = 0.744884409668 \times 10^{-6}$
$b_{10} = -0.316765853771 \times 10^{-5}$	$b_{21} = -0.107686044002 \times 10^7$	$b_{32} = -0.136758502411 \times 10^{-3}$
$b_{11} = 0.348868332019 \times 10^{-2}$	$b_{22} = 0.537117265673 \times 10^3$	
$\rho_{cr} = 10.63 \text{ [mole/dm}^3\text{]}$	$\gamma = 1$	

Table 4: Coefficients of the CO₂ equation of state.

A.2 The diffusion coefficient for CO₂ in sea water

The diffusion coefficient for CO₂ in water, D_{CO_2} , is a well-known experimental determined quantity. For water at 25 °C, salinity 36 ppm and atmospheric pressure, we adopt the value (Tse and Sandall, 1979)

$$\kappa_d^0 = 1.94 \times 10^{-9} m^2/s \quad (45)$$

For diffusion in liquids, the Stoke-Einstein relation (Lerman, 1979)

$$\frac{\kappa_d^0(T, p)\eta(T, p)}{T} = \frac{\kappa_d^0(T_1, p_1)\eta(T_1, p_1)}{T_1}, \quad (46)$$

where temperature T is in Kelvin, and T_1, p_1 is one point where κ_d^0 and η , the molecular viscosity of sea water, are known. (46) can be used to extrapolate the value of κ_d^0 to other temperatures and pressures. This gives the equation

$$\kappa_d^0(T, p) = \frac{\kappa_d^0(T_1, p_1)\eta(T_1, p_1)T}{T_1\eta(T, p)} = 7.1141 \times 10^{-15} \frac{T}{\eta} \quad (47)$$

where we can use (45), $T_1 = 273.15 + 25K$, $P_1 = 1atm$, and $\eta(298.15K, 1atm) = 1.075 \times 10^{-3}$.

B A rising plume test

As a test of the model a freshwater release with its subsequent rising plume has been done. According to the theory from (Fischer *et al.*, 1979). The key parameters to such a plume are the initial volume, momentum and buoyancy fluxes. They are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} Q &= AW, & \text{Initial volume flux} \\ M &= AW^2, & \text{Initial momentum flux} \\ B &= g'_0 Q, & \text{Initial buoyancy flux} \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

Here g'_0 [ms^{-2}] represent the initial reduced gravity

$$g'_0 = g \frac{\Delta\rho_0}{\rho} \quad (49)$$

and A [m^2] the initial cross sectional area of the plume. For the released water to form a plume and not a jet the initial volume flux must be larger than the released momentum flux, i.e., the velocity should be small. Another restriction is that the Freud number

$$\cap F = \frac{W}{\sqrt{g'_0 \Delta x}} \quad (50)$$

should be greater than 1 in order for the plume to fill the whole release area, (E. E. Adams, personal communication). The stratification will influence on the rising plume, and the stratification is given

$$\rho = \rho_0(1 - \epsilon(z)) \quad (51)$$

where z is in the vertical direction. The density stratification is thereby given by $g\epsilon'$, the derivative of the density multiplied by the constant of gravity. According to (Fischer *et al.*, 1979) the plume terminal height will be

$$h_B = 3.8 \frac{B^{1/4}}{(g\epsilon')^{3/8}} [m] \quad (52)$$

with a possible overshoot. This height represent the neutral buoyancy and is the height in which the plume will spread in the horizontal direction. The overshoot will occur just above the release point with surrounding descending water down to the terminal height.

In this performance test we set up a model domain with 31 meters in the horizontal directions and 63 meters in the vertical, with 63 nodes in each direction the spatial resolution is ~ 0.5 m in the horizontal and 1 m in the vertical. The stratification is set up with a linear temperature profile ranging from 11.1 °C at the bottom to 17.8 °C at the surface. The salinity is initially 32.5 (ppm) through the whole domain. This gives a density ranging from 1025.1 (kgm^{-3}) at the bottom to 1023.4 $kg m^{-3}$ at the surface giving

$$g\epsilon' = 2.6 \times 10^{-4} [s^{-1}] \quad (53)$$

The release has a velocity of ~ 0.5 [$m s^{-2}$], and temperature 17.8 °C resulting in a density of 998 [kgm^{-3}] and a reduced gravity $g'_0 = 0.27$ [$m s^{-2}$]. The Froude number is ~ 1.4 .

The terminal height of the plume will according to Eq. 52 be

$$B \sim 3.4 \times 10^{-2} \frac{m^4}{s^3} \quad (54)$$

$$h_B \sim 36. m \quad (55)$$

Fig. (16) shows the results after 14 minutes. The upper left panel shows the tracer concentrations. The injected freshwater contains a passive tracer with 20 m^{-3} which is used as a measure of the spreading of the plume water. The upper right panels shows the density, notice that the stratification is gradually destroyed the heavier water is changed with lighter water. The lower panels shows the horizontal and vertical velocity components in the cross-section.

Figure 16: A vertical cross-section through the inlet. The upper panels shows tracer concentration, density (kgm^{-3}) while the lower panels are the horizontal and vertical velocity (both ms^{-1}).

Notice how the plume entrain water at the inlet while the plume spreads above 30 meters. The vertical velocity shows how the plume water overshoot the level of neutral buoyancy resulting in sinking water on the outer perimeter of the plume. The plume spreads between 30 and 40 meters.

Notation			
α_c	[1]	volume fraction continuous phase	Eq. (3)
α_d	[1]	volume fraction dispersed phase	Eq. (2)
β_d	$[kg\ m^{-3}\ s^{-1}]$	Drag coefficient single droplet	Eq. (30)
β_V	$[kg\ m^{-3}\ s^{-1}]$	Drag coefficient	Eq. (31)
K	$[m\ s^{-1}]$	Mass transfer coefficient CO ₂	Eq. (35)
$\kappa_C^0 = 1.8 \times 10^{-9}$	$[m^2\ s^{-1}]$	Molecular diffusivity CO ₂	
κ_C^e	$[m^2\ s^{-1}]$	Turbulent diffusivity CO ₂	p. 14
$\kappa_S^0 = 1.5 \times 10^{-9}$	$[m^2\ s^{-1}]$	Molecular diffusivity salinity	
κ_S^e	$[m^2\ s^{-1}]$	Turbulent diffusivity salinity	p. 14
$\kappa_T^0 = 1.5 \times 10^{-7}$	$[m^2\ s^{-1}]$	Molecular diffusivity temperature	
κ_T^e	$[m^2\ s^{-1}]$	Turbulent diffusivity temperature	p. 14
μ_0	$[kg\ m^{-1}\ s^{-1}]$	Molecular dynamic viscosity	
ν_0	$[m^2\ s^{-1}]$	Molecular kinematic viscosity	
ν_e	$[m^2\ s^{-1}]$	Eddy kinematic viscosity	(26)
ρ_c	$[kg\ m^{-3}]$	Seawater density	Eq. (24)
$\bar{\rho}_c$	$[kg\ m^{-3}]$	Seawater bulk density	Eq. (6)
ρ_d	$[kg\ m^{-3}]$	CO ₂ density	App. A.1
$\bar{\rho}_d$	$[kg\ m^{-3}]$	CO ₂ bulk density	Eq. (6)
$\tilde{\tau}$	[Pa]	Stress tensor	Eq. (25)
C	$[mole\ m^3]$	CO ₂ concentration	
c_s	[?]	Smagorinsky constant	Eq. (26)
$g = 9.81$	$[m\ s^{-2}]$	Gravitational constant	
K	$[m\ s^{-1}]$	Massdiffusion singel droplet	Eq. (35)
$M_{CO_2} = 44.01 \times 10^{-3}$	$[kg\ mole^{-1}]$	Molecular mass CO ₂	
n	$[m^{-3}]$	number density of droplets	Eqs. (1), (23)

n_{inj}	$[m^{-3}]$	number density of droplets injected	Sec. 3.2.3
p	$[Pa]$	Pressure	Eq. (14)
r	$[m]$	Droplet radius	
S	$[psu]$	Salinity	
s_{mass}	$[kg\ m^{-3}\ s^{-1}]$	Mass transfer	
s_{inj}	$[kg\ m^{-3}\ s^{-1}]$	CO ₂ injection rate	
T	$[^{\circ}C]$	Temperature	
U_T	$[m\ s^{-1}]$	Terminal or slip velocity	Eq. (38)
u	$[m\ s^{-1}]$	Seawater velocity	
v	$[m\ s^{-1}]$	Droplet velocity	
$v_{CO_2} = 34 \times 10^{-6}$	$[m^3\ mole^{-1}]$	Molar volume of CO ₂	
V_d	$[m^3]$	Volume single droplet	

Notation			
α_c	[1]	volume fraction continuous phase	Eq. (3)
α_d	[1]	volume fraction dispersed phase	Eq. (2)
β_d	$[kg\ m^{-3}\ s^{-1}]$	Drag coefficient single droplet	Eq. (30)
β_V	$[kg\ m^{-3}\ s^{-1}]$	Drag coefficient	Eq. (31)
K	$[m\ s^{-1}]$	Mass transfer coefficient CO ₂	Eq. (35)
$\kappa_C^0 = 1.8 \times 10^{-9}$	$[m^2\ s^{-1}]$	Molecular diffusivity CO ₂	
κ_C^e	$[m^2\ s^{-1}]$	Turbulent diffusivity CO ₂	p. 14
$\kappa_S^0 = 1.5 \times 10^{-9}$	$[m^2\ s^{-1}]$	Molecular diffusivity salinity	
κ_S^e	$[m^2\ s^{-1}]$	Turbulent diffusivity salinity	p. 14
$\kappa_T^0 = 1.5 \times 10^{-7}$	$[m^2\ s^{-1}]$	Molecular diffusivity temperature	
κ_T^e	$[m^2\ s^{-1}]$	Turbulent diffusivity temperature	p. 14
μ_0	$[kg\ m^{-1}\ s^{-1}]$	Molecular dynamic viscosity	
ν_0	$[m^2\ s^{-1}]$	Molecular kinematic viscosity	
ν_e	$[m^2\ s^{-1}]$	Eddy kinematic viscosity	(26)
ρ_c	$[kg\ m^{-3}]$	Seawater density	Eq. (24)
$\bar{\rho}_c$	$[kg\ m^{-3}]$	Seawater bulk density	Eq. (6)
ρ_d	$[kg\ m^{-3}]$	CO ₂ density	App. A.1
$\bar{\rho}_d$	$[kg\ m^{-3}]$	CO ₂ bulk density	Eq. (6)
$\bar{\tau}$	[Pa]	Stress tensor	Eq. (25)
C	$[mole\ m^3]$	CO ₂ concentration	
c_s	[?]	Smagorinsky constant	Eq. (26)
$g = 9.81$	$[m\ s^{-2}]$	Gravitational constant	
K	$[m\ s^{-1}]$	Massdiffusion singel droplet	Eq. (35)
$M_{CO_2} = 44.01 \times 10^{-3}$	$[kg\ mole^{-1}]$	Molecular mass CO ₂	
n	$[m^{-3}]$	number density of droplets	Eqs. (1), (23)

Figure 14: Volume ($\times 10^3 \text{ m}^3$) with reduced pH. Upper panels show pH-reduction of 0.1 and 0.5 units while the lower panels shows volume with 1 pH-unit reduction. Labels from Tab. 2

For varying background velocity the highest velocity reaches a steady state after ~ 20 minutes. Until that time the affected volume stays above the Base Case curve since the CO_2 is transported faster downstream. However, the resulting steady state is smaller than the Base Case. The experiment with no velocity do not reach a steady state within the time frame of the experiment. There is background current to transport the CO_2 out of the sampling, and as can be seen in Fig. (15) the CO_2 reaches the bottom at 750 meters and spread over the sea floor. In this experiment the difference between the three curves are not as high as for the other cases, the CO_2 stays in the vicinity of the plume area and less dilution is taking place.

The volume of reduced pH when the injection rate is reduced by a factor 10 is much lower, there are an order of magnitude less CO_2 in the water masses.

To see how the CO_2 is distributed in the vertical, Fig. (15) shows the fraction of the total CO_2 in the sampling box as function of depth. The escape of some of the CO_2 in the R12 case can be seen. Also notice how the CO_2 is distributed deeper for the low radius case, R01. Low injection rate narrows the CO_2 layer. Higher background currents also narrow the CO_2